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Research Article

**REGIONAL SOCIO-ECONOMIC POLICIES FOR THE
DEVELOPMENT OF COASTAL AREAS AND MARINE
ACTIVITIES**¹Tamara Tsatchlanova, ²Namina Burkutbaeva, ³Elzata Erdnieva, ⁴Savr Namysov,
⁵Danara Erendzhenova¹Kalmyk State University named after B. B. Gorodovikov, Elista, Russia.**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

The article assesses the current state of development of coastal areas and marine activities in the Russian Federation on the example of the Republic of Kalmykia. In particular, a strategic analysis of positive and negative factors characterizing the development of coastal areas and the maritime activities of the region is presented. Particular attention is paid to the priority areas of integrated coastal zone management in the framework of strategic planning of the regional economy.

Key words: *Integrated Development, Marine Activities, Coastal Area, Region, Socio-Economic Development.*

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SHORT REVIEW:

According to the Strategy for the Development of Maritime Activities until 2030, approved by Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 2205-r of December 8, 2010, the subjects of the Russian Federation are responsible for implementing the strategic task of developing and implementing programs for the integrated development of coastal areas and coastal waters as an independent components of integrated strategies and programs for the socio-economic development of coastal regions of the Russian Federation and programs for the development of coastal municipalities.

For effective coastal management, it is necessary to link the natural environment and human activity into one system. Important components of such an integrated system are: natural processes that create and maintain coastal ecosystems, their state and productivity, coastal ecosystems, resources generated by coastal systems, the potential use of these resources to fulfill the objectives of social and economic development; the type and scale of existing and potential (in the context of changing social, economic and political circumstances) conflicts in the use of resources [3].

The features of integrated coastal zone management (ICZM) are interdisciplinarity, differences in the scale of management (creation of a managerial vertical), dualism of the role of the population (in the context of the ICZM, the population can be considered as internal or external to the coastal territory), priority of strategic planning (compared to other types of planning) [1].

The coastal territories of the Republic of Kalmykia include the territory of the city of Lagan and the Lagansky district. The water area of the Caspian Sea, adjacent to the territory of the region and the city, is rich in fish resources. The sturgeon breeds of fish off the coast of Kalmykia are represented by four species: sturgeon, stellate sturgeon, beluga and sterlet. In coastal waters there is a lot of carp, perch, crucian, pike, catfish and other species of fish of common species. Fish stocks in the industrial zone amount to 29.1 thousand tons. Ilmeni and Eriki, adjacent to the Caspian Sea, are rich in fish.

The fish industry of the Republic of Kalmykia has a high social significance, ensuring employment of citizens in coastal villages and in the city of Lagan. The fishing fleet is updated by the investments of commercial enterprises. Fishing vessels of enterprises and organizations of fisheries of the Republic of

Kalmykia operate in the exclusive economic zone of the Russian Federation.

The forecasted hydrocarbon reserves of the "Kalmyk" sector of the Northern Caspian shelf are over 1 billion tons. The identified oil and gas potential of the Caspian Sea and the implementation of projects for the construction of a fish processing plant in Lagansky District will entail the development of Lagansky commercial port.

The development of the coastal areas of the Republic of Kalmykia is also associated with the recreational potential of these areas. The region has developed tourism programs for ecological tourism, including the Lotus Festival, the Fisherman's Day, and the Day of the Hunter. A promising project is to create an all-season tourist (hunting, fishing) base.

The use of the entire potential of recreational resources of the territory is one of the promising areas of cooperation between regional and foreign travel companies in the organization of environmental, fishing, hunting, ethnic, health and medical and historical tours.

Key positive factors for the development of coastal areas and marine activities of the Republic of Kalmykia (advantages, strengths and favorable opportunities of the external environment):

- favorable economic and geographical location: access to the non-freezing Caspian Sea, the most optimal access to the countries of the Middle East, Western Asia and the Persian Gulf, crossing the North-South transport corridor;
- potential for port construction in accordance with the North-South transport corridor program;
- high level of hydrocarbon deposits in the adjacent "Kalmyk" shelf of the Caspian Sea (over 1 billion tons of oil and gas);
- developed fishing industry, due to consistently high demand for fish products in foreign markets;
- Caspian Sea adjacent to the region is a unique natural landscape attraction, rich in game and fish, which creates favorable conditions for the development of tourism (recreational, including beach; cultural, educational, ecological, rural tourism);
- for social and economic development, there is the necessary labor resources - qualified personnel working at industrial enterprises of the district and currently working in other regions, mainly on a rotational basis;
- significant export potential for growth due to the extraction and processing of aquatic biological resources, the processing of mineral resources;

- availability of continental waters for commercial fish farming [6].
- Negative factors for the development of coastal areas and marine activities of the Republic of Kalmykia, the Republic of Kalmykia (weaknesses, problems and risks, external threats):
- lack of transport, logistics and port infrastructure;
- a short coastline (the total length of the coastline of the region is about 130 km), which opens up small opportunities for the development of foreign trade, sea fishing, and the handling of export and import cargo;
- a weak degree of commodity and geographical diversification of fish and seafood exports, there is practically no high value added processing products in the export of fish and seafood;
- a high degree of wear of the fishing fleet, more than 60 percent of which have a maximum and excess life (over 25 years);
- low concentration of production resources, poorly developed infrastructure in the coastal-marine area;
- natural disasters (floods of the Caspian Sea);
- insufficient financing of the economic development programs of the Lagansky region both at the expense of the regional budget, and at the expense of the public-private partnership;
- the likelihood of low implementation of investment projects due to lack of sufficient infrastructure.
- The ranking of types of marine activities in terms of relevance for the socio-economic development of the Republic of Kalmykia is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Ranking of the types of marine activities in terms of relevance to the socio-economic development of the Republic of Kalmykia

The main directions of development of coastal areas and marine activities in the Republic of Kalmykia will be disclosed in the establishment of a strategic goal and objectives.

The strategic goal is to improve the quality of life standards through the strategic development of coastal areas and the creation of favorable conditions for self-actualization of the living population, the transition to the innovative trajectory of sustainable self-development of the Republic of Kalmykia, the intensification of international cooperation, increasing the competitiveness of the region and its integration into the Russian and global social and economic spaces.

In accordance with the goal, the following tasks should be implemented:

- interaction with federal executive authorities aimed at creating favorable conditions for the development of the coastal zone, attracting investments for the renewal and modernization of sea and coastal economic activities;
- creation of port infrastructure;

- promoting the competitiveness of the maritime industries, the development of export potential, the promotion of products of the maritime industries on the domestic and foreign markets;
- an increase in the production and export of fish and seafood, including due to commodity and geographic diversification of export supplies, the creation of new enterprises in the fish industry;
- creating conditions conducive to attracting and retaining highly qualified personnel for coastal and marine activities;
- an increase in the export of tourist services due to the development of sea tourism and recreation, creating the image of a tourist region;
- promotion of large interregional infrastructure projects that are important for the integrated development of several Russian regions, such as: the development of port infrastructure in the Astrakhan region, the Republic of Dagestan and the Republic of Kalmykia;
- creation of favorable conditions, introduction of benefits and preferences in order to attract investments from other Russian subjects for the implementation of projects in the region.

- Priority measures for the development of coastal areas and marine activities of the Republic of Kalmykia are:
- construction of a modern international port component “Port Lagan” with a design capacity of 22.5 million tons per year with subsequent connection to the Caspian export-import hub;
- development of fish farming on small bodies of water on the Caspian coast, which are not currently involved in artificial reproduction processes;
- geological exploration on the shelf of the Caspian Sea, the development of new fields and the development of the oil and gas industry;
- support of projects in the field of ecological and cruise tourism;
- personnel training for the fishery and tourist complexes;
- warning and assessment of anthropogenic impact on the state of natural complexes;
- cleaning the Caspian Sea from the pollution of sea waters from sunken ships.
- The target vision of the coastal-marine component of the Strategy for Social and Economic Development of the Republic of Kalmykia until 2030 includes the implementation of the flagship project “Caspian Sea - Kalmykia Growth Driver”, which is a long-term inter-sectoral project creating a comprehensive vision of the development of coastal areas and marine activities with municipalities within the area.
- As part of the flagship project, the following priority projects are being developed and implemented:
 - “Construction of a seaport in the city of Lagan” with subsequent connection to the Caspian export-import hub (Astrakhan Region, Republic of Dagestan, Republic of Kalmykia)”;
 - “Construction of an oil refinery in Ulan-Khol”;
 - “Construction of a wool processing factory in the village. Dzhalykovo, Lagansky district”;
 - “Construction of a gas chemical plant with a line for the production of granulated sulfur and a chemical plant for the production of mineral fertilizers based on the processing of hydrocarbon raw materials (ammonia) in the village Artesian of Chernozemelsky district ”;
 - “Construction of the Lagansky fish-breeding complex for the reproduction of valuable commercial fish species”;
 - “Journey to the country of Bumba”. (Fig. 2)

The purpose of identifying priority projects is the possibility of developing local strategies for socio-economic development, consolidated infrastructure and sectoral schemes for prospective territorial entities of the region. These long-term planning documents set the integrated vision of the desired future of the territories of two municipalities at the same time, identify key inter-municipal projects that enhance the synergistic effects of socio-economic development, increase the attractiveness of the territory for business, the quality of life of the population (welfare, social security, development of cultural, social and infrastructural environment), determining the conditions for ensuring the preservation of natural landscapes.

Figure 2: Structure of the Flagship project “Caspian Sea - Kalmykia Growth Driver”

Table 1 presents key indicators of the effectiveness of the implementation of the proposed project for integrated development of coastal areas and marine activities in the region.

Table 1: Key indicators of the implementation of the Flagship project "Caspian Sea - Kalmykia's Growth Driver"

Indicator	2019	2020	2021	2024	2027	2030
Improving quality of life standards through strategic planning of the development of coastal areas and creating favorable conditions for self-realization of the population, transition to an innovative trajectory of sustainable self-development of the Republic of Kalmykia, intensifying international cooperation, enhancing the competitiveness of the region and its integration into the Russian and global social and economic space						
Investments, billion rubles	14,0	14,78	12,52	15,0	15,3	15,8
Number of newly created jobs, thousand people	-	-	0,5	2,5	3,0	3,5

CONCLUSION:

The expected results of the implementation of the Flagship project will be:

- increasing the level of socio-economic development of the Republic of Kalmykia;
- creation of a transport and logistics center in the Republic of Kalmykia;
- improving the quality of public service by air, rail and road;
- creation of a land-based production base of transport infrastructure facilities of the Republic of Kalmykia;
- creation of infrastructure for the carriage of goods by sea;
- creation of the tourism industry infrastructure that meets modern requirements;
- the creation of new jobs;
- the growth of tourist flow;
- improving the quality of life of the population of the region.

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